

**D5.7 Second annual report on
dissemination activities to
international stakeholders**

**WP5 Science to Policy
Translation to stakeholders**

Responsible Partner: SSI

Contributing partners: BfR, PMT members

GENERAL INFORMATION

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1. Summary

This report describes the dissemination activities of WP5 of One Health EJP during Y2. During Y2, two Stakeholders Committee meetings were held, and dissemination strategy was taken into action. Reach out to international stakeholders was continuously broadened and well received.

2. Highlights

- Contacts and dialogue continued actively between the One Health EJP and the Key EU Stakeholders ECDC and EFSA
- More contacts established between specific projects (ORION, COHESIVE, NOVA) within the One Health EJP and representatives of ECDC and EFSA
- Two Stakeholders Committee meetings held (21st of May 2019 and 12th of November 2019), where additional stakeholders were invited
- Representatives of ECDC and EFSA participated and gave an invited presentation at the Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM, 22nd-24th of May 2019)
- Letters of intent and full proposals of 2nd call projects were disseminated to ECDC and EFSA; the feedback was taken into account during the preparation and selection process, and will be also considered in the implementation phase
- Representatives of ECDC and EFSA were invited at the Kick-off Meeting of 2nd call projects (13th of November 2019)
- Dissemination strategy of WP5 was tested in action: two targeted reports were disseminated to ECDC and EFSA
- Development of the “capacity map” progressed based on input from Project Management Team and stakeholders
- Documents describing how the work of the One Health EJP might address the identified needs of international stakeholders (FAO, OIE and WHO), European Environment Agency (EEA) and European Medicines Agency (EMA) were produced and disseminated to the respective organisations
- Contacts with FAO, OIE and WHO-Europe were established through emails and meetings
- Plans for a high-level meeting to be held at ECDC in Y3, gathering ECDC, EFSA, the Programme Managers Committee (PMC), the Programme Owners Committee (POC) and EC DGs, was received positively by both Key EU Stakeholders. This meeting will be the

opportunity to demonstrate the benefit the One Health EJP can have towards national/EU risk assessors and policy makers, as well as addressing possible ways to sustain the One Health EJP after the EU funding period.

- Dissemination Procedure and Scientific Publication Policy were drafted with the aim of maximizing efficiency of dissemination to a broader range of stakeholders within and outside the One Health EJP

3. Description of the activities

Dissemination is defined as follows: “The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.” (EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

Focus in dissemination activities is on making results and outputs available so that they can be used by others. Dissemination is thus disclosure of the results in an attractive and user-friendly way. Dissemination is spreading the new knowledge as widely as possible – but in a targeted manner that focuses on target audiences that can make best use of the results.

WP5 dissemination activities are complementary to the general dissemination activities of the One Health EJP (WP1, Communications team). The general dissemination activities include e.g. that scientific publications and other outcomes yielded by the One Health EJP are quickly made available on the website of the One Health EJP (WP1). Stakeholders are encouraged to use these materials, and their usage is promoted during formal contacts. For example the targeted reports, distributed every six months to ECDC and EFSA in the form of clickable pdf files, facilitate linkage with the One Health EJP website, social media, and with projects’ webpages and resources. Likewise, during the Stakeholders Committee meetings, the usage of the “groups” of the One Health EJP website is clarified.

WP5 dissemination activities address specific groups: Key EU Stakeholders, Stakeholders Committee, Communication Team and all stakeholders. The activities focus largely on facilitating diffusion and use of knowledge. Transactional aspects, linking the providers and users of the knowledge, are also included. Moreover, there are social change aspects: the EJP advocates One Health approach by enhancing and facilitating access and use of the One Health results.

During Y2, the dissemination activities focused on Key EU Stakeholders and international stakeholders. Contacts were reinforced with ECDC and EFSA and established with other international stakeholders organizations (FAO, OIE and WHO).

Due to internal re-organisation at ECDC, the One Health EJP contact person could not continue her engagement and therefore was not present at the 4th SCM. Special attention should be allocated to ensure a smooth change of the main contact person at ECDC.

Two **Stakeholders Committee meetings** were organized to foster interaction with Key European Stakeholders, international stakeholders, as well as with relevant EU-funded projects (COMPARE, EFFORT, EU-JAMRAI and JPI-AMR). One Stakeholders Committee meeting was organized in May 2019 and focused on the PMT and Key EU Stakeholders (ECDC, EFSA), to ensure that One Health EJP is aware of research needs of ECDC and EFSA, to discuss synergies and impact of One Health EJP and to disseminate targeted results. Another Stakeholders Committee meeting was organized in November 2019 and all members of the Stakeholders Committee were invited: the Key EU stakeholders ECDC and EFSA, and the EU-projects COMPARE, EFFORT, JPI-AMR and, for the first time, EU-JAMRAI as well as international stakeholders. Aims of this meeting were to identify synergies, share information to avoid redundancy and disseminate results of the One Health EJP. The Stakeholders Meetings took place in conjunction with main events of the One Health EJP, the Annual Scientific Meeting 2019 and the Kick-off Meeting for 2nd call projects, respectively, in order to ease the participation of representatives of ECDC and EFSA in these events.

To keep Key European Stakeholders up to date with the scientific and integrative output of the One Health EJP, two **targeted reports** were disseminated, containing brief updates on projects of particular interest for ECDC and EFSA, as well as general announcements of the consortium.

To maximize the impact that 2nd call projects could have for ECDC and EFSA, **letters of intent** and successively **full proposals** were disseminated, and two rounds of feedback were held between candidate projects and Key European Stakeholders. This process was conducted in collaboration with WP3 and WP4.

To broaden the dissemination activities of WP5, representatives from international stakeholders **FAO, OIE and WHO** were contacted via mail and meetings with them were carried out and are planned for Y3.

Given the scientific and integrative output of the One Health EJP in the field of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), the **European Medicines Agency (EMA)** was also contacted. Moreover, as four of the upcoming 2nd call projects will deal directly with environmental topics, the **European Environment Agency (EEA)** was also contacted as a putative further target of dissemination activities of WP5.

Three documents (attached to this report) were drafted to highlight how work carried out by the One Health EJP may have impact on the identified needs of prospective stakeholders. One document takes into consideration the **needs of international organizations** FAO, OIE, WHO (as the three organisations often associate under the name Tripartite when dealing with One Health issues); one of EEA; and one of EMA. These documents have been disseminated to the FAO, OIE and WHO to underline the impact that activities of the One Health EJP can have beyond the European borders and to encourage such organizations to make use of tools developed by the One Health EJP. EEA and EMA were also recipients of such documents, to highlight the work of the One Health EJP in the field of environment and antimicrobial resistance, respectively.

To maximize the visibility of WP5 dissemination activities, **presentations** were given at the Programme Managers Committee (PMC) meeting, attended by directors and CEOs, and at the two Scientific Steering Board (SSB) meeting of 2019, attended by scientific directors / head of departments of consortium members' institutes. A **poster** was presented at the One Health EJP first Annual Scientific Meeting (ASM), attended by consortium members as well as external participants.

At the national policy level, the objectives and activities of WP5 were illustrated at the Programme Owners Committee (POC) meeting, attended by national ministries of authority.

Fostering communication with other EU projects is within the scope of WP5, aiming to avoid duplication of work, ensure complementarity, and eventually maximize the impact of the One

Health EJP activities. This was not limited to inviting COMPARE, EFFORT, EU-JAMRAI and JPI-AMR at our Stakeholders Committee Meeting, but WP5 representatives also gave a presentation at meetings of JPI-AMR.

WP5 carries on regular scanning of stakeholders' documents (EEA, EFSA, ECDC, EMA, FAO, OIE, WHO etc.) in order to identify newly upcoming research and integrative needs of stakeholders and establish interactions where complementarity may be feasible (this activity is described in detail in the One Health EJP Periodic Technical Report Year 2). Information extracted following this process are then used not just by WP5, but are also shared with the One Health EJP Communication Team, to support their means of dissemination (e.g. social media).

To clarify the means of dissemination to a broader range of stakeholders, additional documents were drafted: a **Dissemination Procedure** protocol and the **Scientific Publication Policy**. The Dissemination Procedure was drafted in collaboration with WP1, WP2, WP3 and WP4, and “describes the flow of outputs (i.e. OHEJP [One Health EJP], JRP, JIP and PhD deliverables and publications) during their drafting and finalization with the aim of maximizing efficiency of dissemination within and outside the OHEJP”. The Scientific Publication Policy was drafted by WP3 and WP4 and “sets out guidelines for producing research communication (oral or written) under the OHEJP. The main purpose of this policy is to guarantee that the scientific outputs using a peer-review process, generated from the OHEJP, are published to the maximum possible scientific standard, using a coordinated and appropriate approach”.

These dissemination activities will continue actively in Y3. Newly upcoming results for research projects and integrative activities will be disseminated using the means described in Dissemination strategy (D5.5). The next major dissemination activity will be the second ASM in 2020. The “capacity map” of WP5 (D5.4) will be one of the means for the One Health EJP to reach out to various stakeholders. After thorough discussion with the PMT and with the stakeholders, the aim and content of the “capacity map” were focused during year 2, as well as the target audience: the “capacity map” was seen as a valuable tool for dissemination of results to national and international stakeholders, to other One Health initiatives, as well as within the One Health EJP, to support collaboration (e.g. between first and second round projects) and to minimize the risk of duplication of work. Technical implementation is ongoing and the “capacity map” will be functional in Y3.

Two tailored reports will be produced in Y3 and disseminated to Key EU Stakeholders, and two Stakeholder Meetings will be held. An additional meeting is planned to be held at ECDC and aims to further strengthen the collaboration with the Key EU Stakeholders.

4. Evaluation, impact and potential

WP5 “Science to Policy Translation” has been actively working on dissemination activities during Y2 having as main objectives to foster the dialogue with stakeholders, and to improve the awareness on and uptake of tools, scientific and integrative output of the One Health EJP by risk assessors and policy initiatives. The structures for efficient dissemination are in place, in use, and were further adjusted based on dialogue with the Stakeholders.

Efficient uptake and use of the results maximizes the impact of the projects and, in general, of the One Health EJP. Key EU stakeholders are in the position to identify which gaps, when filled or bridged, can have the highest value for informing decision-making in EU to strengthen EU resilience the most. One Health EJP fills such gaps and efficient and timely dissemination of the results has major potential for impact.

In line with the feedback from REA Steering Group, WP5 together with the PMT continues to monitor and highlight the impact (specifically, 1. Expertise that has been built up, 2. New data, 3. Scientific publications, and additionally 4. Cross-sectoral alignment and integration).

5. Attachments

- Links between needs of international stakeholders (FAO, OIE, WHO) and One Health EJP expertise
- Links between needs of EMA and One Health EJP expertise
- Links between needs of the European Environment Agency and One Health EJP expertise